

STUDIES ON INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF POST-HARVEST FUNGAL SPOILAGE OF MANGO FRUIT IN BAUCHI STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated the incidence and prevalence of post-harvest fungal spoilage of Mango fruit in Bauchi state. Fungal isolate were identified, and their occurrence, re-isolation rates, and measurement over time were analyzed. The findings revealed the prevalence and persistence of specific fungal species, including *Aspergillus niger* and *Collectorium acutatum*, which accounted for 17.64% and 29.41% of the occurrences respectively. Measurement of these isolate exhibited varying trends, with *Aspergillus niger* showing an increasing from 0.57 to 4.03 over the observed period. Continuous monitoring and risk assessment are recommended to track the presence and evaluate potential health risk associated with these prevalent fungal isolates. Interdisciplinary collaboration among mycologists, environmental health expert and stake holders are encouraged to gain a comprehensive understanding of fungal dynamics and develop holistic strategies for control and prevention. These finding can inform future research and proactive measure aimed at reducing spoilage and ensuring the quality and safety of Mango fruit in the region.

Keywords: Incidence, Prevalence, Post-harvest, Spoilage, Mango fruit, Bauchi State

Introduction

Mango (*Mangifera Indica L.*) is an important tropical fruit crop in Nigeria, and its production has a long history in the country. The first mango trees were introduced into Nigeria by Portuguese explorers in the 15th century, and mango production has since spread to all part of the country (Adegbite, *et al.*, 2018). The fruits is widely grown in the southern and middle belt region of the country where the climate is suitable for its cultivation. Over the years, mango production in Nigeria has increased significantly due to the high demand for the fruit both domestically and for export. The Nigerian government has implemented several policies and programs to support the growth of the mango industries, such as the National Horticultural research institute (NIHORT) (Adeyemo, *et al.*, 2019). This initiative has helped to increase productivity and reduce postharvest losses, resulting in increased revenue for farmers and the country as a whole. The economic value of fresh mango fruits to most household especially in the rural areas of Nigeria cannot be overestimated as most families depend greatly on the income they make from mango for their livelihood (Onyeani, *et al.*, 2012).

Mango fruit is a good source of polyphenols, ascorbic acid, carotenoids, vitamin and carbohydrates (Singh, *et al.*, 2013). The nutritional properties of mango, especially antioxidants, are essential for human health as they known to boost the immune system and also prevent cardiovascular diseases and various types of cancers (Muhammad *et al.*, 2014).

Sivakumar, *et al.*, (2011). The fruit is susceptible to various postharvest diseases such as anthracnose, and physiological disorder including chilling, injury, spongy tissue and lenticel sport, unfortunately, those individual problems or their combination may result in postharvest losses as well as loss of revenue for the producers and everyone involved in the postharvest value chain. A significant proportion of losses of mango occur during storage and transportation as a result of poor handling and improper facilities (Sivakumar, *et al.*, 2011).

There is no mango variety or cultivars include those found in Nigeria that has been documented to be completely resistance, to fungal rot diseases (Tarnowski, and Ploetz, 2008) (Ponday *et al.*, 2012). There are number of fungi that attack mango fruit at maturity after removal from the tree. Those fungi cause infection during storage and transit, and losses, sustained due to fungal infection during that period are quit heavy. Fruit losses after harvest are also expected to be high due to poor transportation, handling practice and extended storage period (Chala, *et al.*, 2014).

Colletotrichum gloeosporioides and *Botryodiplodia theobromae* are the two major fungi that have been reported to cause damage to mango fruit. *Anthracnose* caused by *C. gloeosporioides* is the major pre and post-harvest diseases of mango in all mango producing areas of the world and is associated with high rainfall and humidity (Fitzell, *et al.*, 1992). Several factors have been identified to contribute to the postharvest fungal spoilage of mango fruit in Nigeria.

These factors include poor handling practices, inadequate storage facilities, inadequate postharvest handling practices, improper storage conditions and the use of contaminated for irrigation and environmental conditions. Inadequate storage facilities and poor handling practices such as bruising and cutting during harvest and transportation can create entry points for fungal infection. Additionally, high humidity, high temperature, and poor ventilation in storage facilities can create a conducive environment for fungal growth and proliferation (Akande, *et al.*, 2017; Olorunda, *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, the lack of effective treatment such as hot water treatment, fumigation and use of fungicides also contribute to postharvest fungal spoilage of mango fruits in Nigeria, (Adejumo *et al.*, 2021). Improper storage conditions were identified as the major factor contributing to postharvest fungal spoilage of mango fruit in Oyo in Nigeria.

Materials and Method

Description of the Study Area

The study was carried out in three local government area of Bauchi State (Fig. 1). Bauchi State North-East of Nigeria, is located between latitude $9^{\circ} 3'$ and $12^{\circ} 3'$ North and longitudes $8^{\circ} 50'$ and 11° east, with a land area of $549,260\text{km}^2$. The state is bordered by seven states, Kano and Jigawa to the North, Taraba and Plateau to the South, Gombe and Yobe to the East and Kaduna to the West. Bauchi state has the projected population of over 6,537,314 inhabitants in the 20 local government areas. The main annual rainfall range between 1300mm per annum in the South and only 700mm per annum in the extreme North. Farmers in Bauchi state specialize in production of food and horticultural crops. For horticultural crops tomatoes, water, melon and mango is widely practiced for both domestic and commercial purposes.

Fig. 1: Map of Bauchi state showing the study area

Collection of Infected Fruit Samples

Farms and market centres in Darazo, Toro and Tafawa Balewa local government area were targeted for the survey. Infected mango fruit samples were identified by physical examination and then collected randomly from the local market like papa, Kwankiyel, Zalau, Rishi and Tilau and from individual farms (plate 3.1). One hundred and fifty (150) fruits with various rot symptoms were collected, placed in polythene bags and brought to the microbiology laboratory, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, for processing and further analysis.

Plate 1: Infected mango fruits collected from farms and markets in Bauchi State

Isolation of Pathogenic Fungi from Rotting Fruits

Potato dextrose agar (PDA) was the standard media used to isolate the fungal pathogen from the fruits. The infected mango samples were first washed under a running tap, then dipped into 1% sodium hydrochloride to surface sterilized for three minutes and rinsed in there change of sterile distilled water. They were then bottled dry by using sterile blating popper.

Direct planting method was used in isolation of the fungal pathogen. A sterile scalpel was used to cut 3 mm x 3, sections of tissue from the mango moving from the healthy portions to the decayed portion where the pathogens are likely to be more active. The pieces were dried using tissue were directly planted on sterile (PDA) and then incubated in the laboratory at room temperature (25⁰C) for 5 days (Plate 3.2).

Plate 2: Direct planting of infected mango tissue in sterile PDA plates

Fungal Identification

Each isolate was subjected to colony and microscopic examinations during which their morphological features were observed and recorded. Identification of the fungi was based on growth potters, color of mycelia and microscopic examinations of vegetative and reproductive structures.

Pathogenicity Test

Pathogenicity test was carried out using the technique described by Okogbo et al., (2019). Healthy mango samples were obtained from the farmers in Darazo, Toro and Tafawa Balewa villages and brought to micro-biology laboratory at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi in polythene bags. The mangoes were then washed under running tap to eliminate dirt from their surfaces. They were surfaced sterilized in 1% NaOCl for three minutes. Thereafter, they were rinsed in three changes of sterile distilled water and wiped dry using a sterile blotting paper.

A sterile (5mm) cork borer was used to puch the mangoes and the discs removed. The same size of the cork borer was used to cut sections of each of the cultures of the previously isolated fungal pathogens and the discs were used to inoculate the healthy wounded mangoes (Elmougy, *et al.*, 2004). The wound on the inoculated mangoes was sealed using sterile transparent adhesive tape. Three mangoes were placed in each sterile polythene bag as a treatment, replicate four times and stored at room temperature (25⁰C) in the laboratory. Diseases development was checked after two days. The pathogens were re-isolated and identified as described earlier.

Method of Data Analysis

Data for this research work were analyses using inferential statistics (ANOVA).

Results and Discussion

Fungi Isolates associated with post- harvest spoilage of Mango fruits

The table shows the fungi isolates associated with post-harvest spoilage of mango fruits. The study identified a total of seven fungi isolates, with *Collectorium acutatum* being the most prevalent (29.41%). *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium* species were also identified, accounting for 17.64% and 14.70% of the isolates, respectively.

Table 1: Fungi Isolates associated with post- harvest spoilage of Mango fruits

S/N	Isolates	No of Occurrences	Percentage of Occurrences (%)
1	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	3	8.82
2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	6	17.64
3	<i>Penicillium species</i>	5	14.70
4	<i>Rhizopus oryza</i>	4	11.76
5	<i>Alternaria alternate</i>	3	8.82
6	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	3	8.82
7	<i>Collectorium acutatum</i>	10	29.41
	Total	34	100%

(Source: Lab Experiment, 2022)

Pathogenicity test of isolates

The result of pathogenicity test from this study revealed that all mango fruits showed symptom of rot while the uninoculated control fruits showed no symptoms of rot. The result indicated that three out of the seven isolates tested (*A. Niger*, *Penicillium species*, and *Rhizopus oryza*) were able to cause spoilage in mango fruits, as they were re-isolated from the infected fruits. The other four isolates *A. Flavus*, *A. Alternate*, *A. nidulans*, and *C. acutatum*) were not able to cause spoilage in mango fruits, as they were not re-isolated from the infected fruits. These result suggested that *A. niger*, *penicillium species* and *R. oryza* may be the responsible for the post-harvest spoilage of mango fruits in Bauchi state. The result agreed with that of Macha, *et al.*, (2020). In India, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillium species* were identify as the major fungi associated with postharvest spoilage of mango fruits. Another study by Santhanam, *et al.*, (2019) in Malaysia identified *Aspergillus niger*, *penicillium species* and *Rhizopus oryzae* as the major fungi responsible for the postharvest spoilage of mango fruits.

Table 2: Pathogenicity test of isolates.

S/N	Fungi	Re-isolated (Yes/No)
1	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	No
2	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Yes
3	<i>Penicillium species</i>	Yes
4	<i>Rhizopus oryza</i>	Yes
5	<i>Alternaria alternate</i>	No
6	<i>Aspergillus nidulans</i>	No
7	<i>Collectorium acutatum</i>	Yes

(Source: Lab Experiment, 2022)

Means and Standard Deviations for Lesion as a function of a 7(Isolate) X 5(Day) design

The table provides information on the mean and standard deviation of fungal isolates' growth on five different days (Day 2-6) in a laboratory study. The marginal totals provide the overall mean and standard deviation for each fungal isolate. There are seven fungal isolates listed in the table, including A.flavus, A.nidulans, A.niger, Alternaria alternate, C.acutatum, P.species, and R.oryza. For each isolate, the table shows their mean and standard deviation of growth on each of the five days. The mean growth of each isolate generally increased over time, from Day 2 to Day 6. For example, A.flavus had a mean growth of 0.47 on Day 2, which increased to 3.40 on Day 6. Similarly, A.niger had a mean growth of 0.57 on Day 2, which increased to 4.03 on Day 6. The standard deviation of growth for each isolate also varied between days. For example, A.flavus had a relatively low standard deviation of 0.12 on Day 2, which increased to 1.16 on Day 6. In contrast, C.acutatum had a relatively high standard deviation of 0.40 on Day 4, which decreased to 0.17 on Day 5. The marginal totals show that the overall mean growth of all isolates increased from 0.47 on Day 2 to 3.30 on Day 6, while the overall standard deviation increased from 0.14 on Day 2 to 0.73 on Day 5.

This observation agreed with the report of (Lopez-havez, 2016) which recorded the significant impact of fungal isolate and time on spoilage in fruits and vegetable. Also, highlight the important of understanding the growth pattern of different isolate to develop effective control measure for preventing spoilage in fruits and vegetables.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviations for Lesion as a function of a 7(Isolate) X 5(Day) design

	Day										Marginal	
	2		3		4		5		6			
Isolate	M	SD	M	SD								
A.flavus	0.47	0.12	1.17	0.29	1.83	0.29	3.07	0.12	3.40	0.17	1.99	1.16
A.nidulans	0.37	0.06	1.17	0.29	1.03	0.06	2.53	0.06	2.63	0.06	1.55	0.93
A.niger	0.57	0.06	1.47	0.06	2.40	0.10	3.70	0.17	4.03	0.06	2.43	1.36
Alternaria alternate	0.37	0.06	1.13	0.12	1.03	0.06	2.47	0.06	2.67	0.06	1.53	0.92
C.acutatum	0.70	0.10	1.67	0.29	2.87	0.06	4.43	0.40	4.60	0.17	2.85	1.59
P.species	0.43	0.06	1.33	0.29	1.43	0.06	2.50	0.10	3.03	0.06	1.75	0.96
R.oryza	0.37	0.06	1.03	0.06	1.03	0.06	2.57	0.06	2.73	0.12	1.55	0.97
Marginal	0.47	0.14	1.28	0.28	1.66	0.71	3.04	0.74	3.30	0.73		

Mixed effect model showing variation by Isolate and Time on Lesion

This table presents the results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) test for the source of variation of fungal isolates and time on the spoilage of mango fruits. The table shows the sum of squares (SS), mean squares (MS), the number of degrees of freedom (NumDF) and denominator degrees of freedom (DenDF), F-value and the probability (Pr>F).

The first row "Isolate" shows the results for the effect of different fungal isolates on the spoilage of mango fruits. The sum of squares (SS) is 23.86, the mean squares (MS) is 3.97, the number of degrees of freedom (NumDF) is 6, and the denominator degrees of freedom (DenDF) is 70. The F-value is 170.49, and the probability (Pr>F) is less than 0.00, which means that the effect of fungal isolates is significant on the spoilage of mango fruits.

The second row "Time" shows the results for the effect of time on the spoilage of mango fruits. The sum of squares (SS) is 120.48, the mean squares (MS) is 30.12, the number of degrees of freedom (NumDF) is 4, and the denominator degrees of freedom (DenDF) is 70. The F-value is 1290.90, and the probability (Pr>F) is less than 0.00, which means that the effect of time is highly significant on the spoilage of mango fruits.

The third row "Isolate: Time" shows the results for the interaction effect of different fungal isolates and time on the spoilage of mango fruits. The sum of squares (SS) is 7.95, the mean squares (MS) is 0.33, the number of degrees of freedom (NumDF) is 24, and the denominator degrees of freedom (DenDF) is 70. The F-value is 14.21, and the probability (Pr>F) is less than 0.00, which means that the interaction effect between fungal isolates and time is significant on the spoilage of mango fruits.

Table 4: Mixed effect model showing variation by Isolate and Time on Lesion

Source of Variation	SS	MS	NumDF	DenDF	F.value	(Pr>F).
Isolate	23.86	3.97	6	70	170.49	<0.00
Time	120.48	30.12	4	70	1290.90	<0.00
Isolate:Time	7.95	0.33	24	70	14.21	<0.00

Note: M and SD represent mean and standard deviation, respectively. Source: Lab Experiment,

Interaction Plot of Lesion (mm) and Time in Day for Isolates

The graph shows that there is an interaction between time and isolates, as the mean growth of each isolate varied over time. This means that the effect of time on the lesion growth -+of each isolate was not constant but varied depending on the isolate. For example, *A.flavus* had a relatively low mean growth on Day 2 but had the highest mean growth on Day 6. In contrast, *A.nidulans* had a relatively high mean growth on Day 2, which increased over time. Similarly, *a.niger* had a relatively high mean growth on Day 2, which continued to increase over time. These patterns suggest that different isolates responded differently to the changing conditions over time. Moreover, the standard deviation of growth also varied over time for each isolate, indicating that the variability in growth was not constant over time. For example, the standard deviation of *A. flavus* growth increased over time, while the standard deviation of *Cacutatum* growth decreased over time.

Fig 2: Interaction Plot of Lesion (mm) and Time in Day for Isolates

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of fungal isolates their occurrence, re- isolation rates, and measurement over time. The findings provide valuable insight into the prevalence and persistence of specific fungal specie in the studies area, by examining the mean and standard deviation measurements; we gained a deeper understanding of the growth pattern and variability of those isolates. The result indicated that *Aspergillus niger* and *Collectorium Acutatum* were the most frequently identified isolates, emphasizing their significance in the studied area. moreover, the- isolation of certain isolates such a *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium* species, *Rhizopus Oryza*, and *Collectrium Acutatum*, suggested their ability to thrive and persist over time. The measurement of the isolates demonstrated variation, with some showly increasing trends over the observation period. Based on these results, it’s recommended to prioritize continuous monitoring and risk assessment efforts to accurately track the presence and evaluate potential health risks associated with prevalent fungal isolates. Interdisciplinary collaboration among expert in mycology, environmental health, and related field should be encourage to foster comprehensive understanding and develop holistic strategies for fungal control and prevention.

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